

Strategizing Business with Opinion Mining and Feature Extraction using Online Customer Reviews on Global Restaurants

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Abstract: In a world that moves fast and with people wanting the best of experiences, targeted marketing is quintessential for any industry. Knowing customer's feedback and what they think is best/ bad about their service is the key to any business. This applies a lot to any industry including food business. With social media platforms, user generated and online contents through such platforms, it makes it easier to gather opinions about businesses. With artificial intelligence (AI) tools to quantify and understand reviews, making business decisions would be a more effective and targeted. In this paper, the researchers focus on using Natural Language Processing (NLP) to learn and decipher the customers' sentiment in the reviews. With the help of supervised learning models, the top positive and negative features about global restaurants were extracted from the thousands of restaurant reviews from online datasets. They were categorized by region to summarize the overall food characteristic of every country. Knowing what is most talked about businesses not only helps the marketers in planning and placing targeted marketing campaigns but also helps in deriving the most value out of them. On the other hand, this will also help the customers make better and faster decisions when they want to make informed choices.

Keywords: *Customer, Opinion, Reviews, Restaurants, Sentiment Analysis.*

INTRODUCTION

Social media content and web content has stirred much excitement and created abundant opportunities for understanding the opinions of the general public and consumers toward social events, political movements, company strategies, marketing campaigns, and product preferences. Many business-related research questions can be answered by analyzing the thousands, even millions, of comments and responses expressed in various social media and social network sites and tweets. With the growing availability and popularity of web-based opinion platforms, online product reviews are now an emerging market phenomenon that is playing an increasingly important role in consumer purchase decisions. Analyzing data from user-generated websites with data mining practices can suggest meaningful insights into services performances. Such techniques may help identifying the precursors of service satisfiers and dis-satisfiers of restaurants.

What makes a good restaurant? What are its key characteristics? What do people say about the restaurant? Is it a crowd favorite? Answers to these questions can be obtained by analyzing the huge repository of opinions from common people on restaurants and diners. Users' reviews or posts are increasing day by day. Records identified with items on the Web, which are functional to both makers and clients. The process of finding user opinion about the topic or product or problem is called as opinion mining. It is the process of automatic extraction of knowledge by means of opinions expressed by the user who is currently using the product about some product.

Consumer sentiment analysis is a recent fad for social media-related applications such as healthcare, hospitality, finance, travel, etc. Disentangling consumer perception to gain insight into the desired objective and reviews is significant. With the advancement of technology, a massive amount of social web data increasing in volume, subjectivity, and heterogeneity becomes challenging to process manually. Artificial Intelligence (AI) techniques have been utilized to handle this difficulty in real-life applications. One such AI tool - Sentiment Analysis is often used in opinion mining to identify sentiment, affect, subjectivity, and other emotional states in online text.

LITERATURE REVIEW

For the purpose of this research, prior literature was reviewed on the application of online sentiment analysis published in refereed international journals over the period 2010-2022.

Online Product Reviews

Retaining customers is more profitable than winning prospective customers. How to retain existing customers and improve their repeat purchases is an important consideration for practitioners to gain profit. Factors influencing customer revisit intention to restaurants were drawn up by analyzing online reviews and it was found that food quality, price and value, service quality, and atmosphere are the antecedents of restaurant customers' revisit intention, and that restaurant type moderates the effect of customer satisfaction with service quality, atmosphere, and price and value on revisit intention. Regression analysis was applied to analyze quantitative scores of 10,136 restaurant reviews collected from an online life community in China, using text mining technology to identify detailed evaluation indicators in each dimension and explore customers' evaluation behavior characteristics. The results are useful for restaurant operators to take effective actions to attract more customers to revisit. (Yan, X., Wang, J., & Chau, M. 2015).

The volume of consumer reviews on the purchase likelihood (conversion rate) of users browsing a product page using the exponential learning curve model to study how conversion rates change with the number of reviews. It was found that on average, the conversion rate of a product can increase by as much as 270% as it accumulates reviews, amongst the users that choose to display them. It was inferred that the existence of reviews provides valuable signals to the customers, increasing their propensity to purchase. It was also inferred that users usually don't pay attention to the entire set of reviews, especially if there are a lot of them, but instead they focus on the first few available. (Askalidis, G., & Malthouse, E. C. 2016).

The economic value of online reviews for consumers and restaurants was analysed from a data set from a leading Chinese website providing user-generated reviews, to study how consumers learn, from reading online reviews, the quality and cost of restaurant dining. A learning model with three novel features was proposed: (1) different reviews offer different informational value to different types of consumers; (2) consumers learn their own preferences, and not the distribution of preferences among the entire population, for multiple product attributes; and (3) consumers update not only the expectation but also the variance of their preferences. (Wu, C. et. al. 2015).

Restaurant Industry – E WOM

Consumer-generated ratings about the quality of food, environment and service of restaurants, and the volume of online consumer reviews are positively associated with the online popularity of restaurants; whereas editor reviews have a negative relationship with consumers' intention to visit a restaurant's webpage. The findings will help hospitality researchers and practitioners better understand the impact of electronic word-of-mouth on purchase decisions. (Zhang, Z. et. al. 2010).

Online recommendation sites are valuable information sources that people contribute to, and often use to choose restaurants. However, little is known about the dynamics behind participation in these online communities and how the recommendations in these communities are formed. This study was undertaken to study the endogenous (i.e., related to entities being reviewed) and exogenous factors influence people's participation in the communities, and to what extent. We find that while endogenous factors such as restaurant attributes (e.g., meal, price, service) affect recommendations, surprisingly, exogenous factors such as demographics (e.g., neighborhood diversity, education) and weather (e.g., temperature, rain, snow, season) also exert a significant effect on reviews. We find that many of the effects in online communities can be explained using offline theories from experimental psychology. Our study is the first to look at exogenous factors and how it related to online online restaurant reviews. It has implications for designing online recommendation sites, and in general, social media and online communities. (Bakhshi, S. et.al. 2014).

By analysing online customer reviews for restaurants, one can underpin the restaurant satisfiers with the nature of online restaurant reviews. Three distinct types of clues – functional, mechanic, and humanic –explain a customer's overall perception of a dining experience that led to satisfaction or dissatisfaction. A focus on food, menu offerings, ambience, and service create buzz in social media. Furthermore, several implications inform customer researchers about effective ways to investigate and serve the restaurant industry. (Bilgihan, A., Seo, S., & Choi, J. 2018)

Investigations into the multi-dimensionality of authenticity as expressed in restaurant contexts have been scarce. By analysing the authenticity judgements from online reviews, one can examine how consumers perceive authenticity in restaurant experiences. Findings suggest the very same entity can be evaluated with respect to more than one dimension of authenticity, thus calling for rigorous understanding of offerings among restaurateurs to project appropriate authenticity cues that appeal to consumers. (Le, T. H. et.al. 2022).

AI Techniques for Sentiment Analysis

An ever-increasing number of results are stored in the web as well as the amount of people acquiring items from web are increasing. Analyzing the emotions from the extracted opinions is made using Sentiment Analysis. The goal of opinion mining and Sentiment Analysis is to make computer able to recognize and express emotion. This work focussed on mining reviews from the websites like Amazon, which allows user to freely write the view by automatically extracting reviews from websites. It also uses algorithm such as Naïve Bayes classifier, Logistic Regression and SentiWordNet algorithm to classify the review as positive and negative review. At the end quality metric parameters were used to measure the performance of each algorithm. (Kumar, K. S. et.al 2016).

The explosion of internet-generated content, coupled with methodologies such as sentiment analysis, present exciting opportunities for marketers to generate market intelligence on consumer attitudes and brand opinions. The paper reviewed the marketing literature on online sentiment analysis and examines the application of sentiment analysis from three main perspectives: the unit of analysis, sampling design and methods used in sentiment detection and statistical analysis. (Rambocas, M., & Pacheco, B. G. 2018)

Positive “word of mouth” is the key to successful innovation diffusion. Innovation managers pay close attention to examine customer sentiment. Online reviews are often the most accessible sources of customer feedback. Online review ratings and online review volume, the two most common metrics to interpret customer sentiment from online reviews, have some critical limitations. Online review ratings are prone to extremity bias since extremely satisfied or dissatisfied customers are most likely to leave online reviews. Online review volume can increase for any reason, and it does not necessarily indicate positive or negative customer feedback. This article explores text mining methods and proposes some alternative metrics to interpret customer sentiment. The findings show that sentiment scores might be less prone to extremity bias compared to online review ratings. Sentiment scores tended to fit a normal distribution while online review ratings were skewed to extreme values. Sentiment scores and review lengths, when combined, can provide a new angle to observe enthusiasm. (Kim, R. Y. 2021)

The usefulness, scope, and applicability of the alliance of AI techniques for consumer sentiment analysis (CSA) using Natural Language Processing (NLP) for online reviews in the domain of hospitality and tourism is massive. This research has significant implications for service providers in terms of developing managerial strategies for consumers in terms of selecting services that meet their needs. Furthermore, there is high impact for researchers in terms of prospective research directions. (Jain, P. K et. Al 2021)

Online product reviews have significant impacts on consumers’ purchase decisions. To support consumers’ purchase decisions, how to rank the products through online reviews is a valuable research topic, while research concerning this issue is still relatively scarce. This paper proposes a method based on the sentiment analysis technique and the intuitionistic fuzzy set theory to rank the products through online reviews. An algorithm based on sentiment dictionaries is developed to identify the positive, neutral or negative sentiment orientation on the alternative product concerning the product feature in each review. Converting the identified positive, neutral and negative sentiment orientations into intuitionistic fuzzy numbers is a new idea for processing and fusing a large number of sentiment orientations of online reviews. Based on the proposed method, decision support system can be developed to support the consumers’ purchase decisions more conveniently. (Liu, Y. et. al. 2017)

METHODS

Data for this research was sourced from Yelp which is an American business directory service and crowd-sourced review forum. It has almost every business listed on the platform and open for consumer review. Since it is a crowd-sourced review forum, it is open-ended, reliable and up-to-date. This paper focussed on the restaurant sector which is the most popular and most reviewed on Yelp. Yelp reviews have become a data playground for researchers and analyzers given that it is wide-spread and up-to-date.

After retrieving usable customer comments on Yelp.com, using a coded web spider, a series of qualitative data analysis techniques were deployed to detect the satisfiers and dis-satisfiers of different types of global restaurants. The analysis was made applying the concepts of Natural Language Processing (NLP) to learn the trends in the restaurant reviews and extract meaningful information and tie them up with a business impact which will give business owners ideas to improve or better their decisions and grow bigger.

FINDINGS

Classification Results

After creating SVM classification models on each of the cuisine types, and extracting the polarity matrix against the words, the final list of top features were extracted from the review dataset. Tabulated below are the positive and negative features/words respectively in the order of their impact.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
cuisine										
American	delicious	friendly	perfection	fresh	outstanding	recommend	comfort	cozy	fast	fun
Mexican	fresh	friendly	fast	solid	reasonable	fun	recommended	authentic	worth	heaven
Italian	friendly	fresh	authentic	perfection	rich	cute	romantic	refreshing	seasoned	quiet
Chinese	fresh	friendly	authentic	perfection	cool	fried	tender	affordable	fast	generous
Japanese	friendly	fast	easy	variety	soft	fresh	interesting	enjoy	sweet	pleasant
Indian	fresh	reasonable	friendly	satisfied	cool	variety	tender	hot	seasoned	clean
Thai	fresh	recommend	hot	fried	attentive	enjoy	clean	hot	popular	interesting
Mediterranean	friendly	fresh	healthy	worth	fancy	helpful	cute	fun	wow	nicely
Greek	fresh	friendly	generous	reasonable	tender	variety	outstanding	soft	seasoned	pleasant
Vietnamese	friendly	attentive	healthy	variety	hot	generous	polite	refreshing	solid	wow
Korean	friendly	fried	fresh	hot	fun	generous	fast	interesting	pleasant	popular
French	friendly	fresh	sweet	lovely	liked	rich	wow	beautiful	mashed	charming
Hawaiian	friendly	fresh	free	healthy	rich	thank	work	worth	hot	outstanding
Spanish	friendly	quiet	variety	memorable	tender	fried	noise	bomb	cheap	modern
African	fun	available	interesting	fried	lemon	free	affordable	reasonably	insanely	attentive

Table 1 – Positive Features Extracted across Global Restaurants

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
cuisine										
American	cold	slow	bland	hard	expensive	weird	frozen	overpriced	greasy	stuck
Mexican	hard	attentive	warm	bland	sad	cold	slow	hot	frozen	greasy
Italian	cold	wrong	free	bland	loud	overpriced	cheap	mediocre	crowded	soft
Chinese	sour	cold	hard	bland	greasy	sweet	rude	weird	sick	sticky
Japanese	bland	problem	crazy	slow	expensive	mediocre	dark	weird	clear	free
Indian	smell	expensive	hard	cold	weird	greasy	overpriced	odd	spicy	free
Thai	hard	sweet	weird	top	cold	slow	greasy	bland	smell	rude
Mediterranean	cold	slow	warm	wrong	bland	weird	hype	stale	poor	overpriced
Greek	hot	hard	warm	lemon	frozen	wrong	solid	awful	crowded	bland
Vietnamese	sweet	fried	bland	broken	limited	smell	slow	comfort	hard	cleanliness
Korean	hard	cold	bland	slow	expensive	weird	strange	damn	sad	crowded
French	warm	cold	perfection	problem	available	slow	comfort	wrong	stuck	overrated
Hawaiian	cold	hard	sweet	strong	wrong	sad	fatty	bitter	sticky	lacked
Spanish	hard	waste	pricey	fell	steep	loud	randomly	limited	oddly	sour
African	cold	cool	poor	overpriced	work	cheapest	rude	fell	confused	lost

Table 2 – Negative Features Extracted across Global Restaurants

Insights

From the positive features, it is observed that the word ‘friendly’ is most frequently used as one of the top few words leading to a positive score, denoting that a friendly ambience and service is more impactful than the quality of food. The word ‘fresh’ closely follows, suggesting that the quality of ingredients used and the cleanliness in service is also a key factor for a high rating. Generally, among the words used for expressing a positive review, the mention about price or cheapness of service is rare. This might also mean that people do not mind paying more as long as they get a cozy, happy ambience with good, tasty and fresh food.

From the negative features, it can be observed that the words 'bland' and 'cold' most frequently contributes to a low rating. Customers seem to consider flavor and how it is served to be an integral part of their dining experience. Also, the word 'overpriced' is usually seemed to be paired with other features like 'cold', 'slow' etc., denoting that people consider food that is not served at right temperatures and being made to wait for service as a waste of the money they have spent.

Also, different types of restaurants seemed to show different characteristics. For example, American and Mexican restaurants are known for being 'fast' and 'fun'. Korean and Japanese restaurants were known for their 'freshness', 'variety' and for being 'pleasant'. While French restaurants are characterized for being aesthetically pleasing, Chinese and Italian places are recognized for being 'authentic'.

Using these insights, one can suggest ways to improve a business and provide useful guidance to do so. For example, to improve business or rating for a Korean restaurant, it might be sensible to prioritize taste as the primary selling point and to take keen attention into serving meat fresh and tender. Making sure the ambience is not too crowded and serving food that is not too sweet and cold will help avoiding sending dissatisfied customers home.

On the other hand, to improve a French restaurant business, one might want to keep the environment clean and fancy. And the food must be aesthetically pleasing, delicious and served generously. Having a comfortable setting with professional waiters is key.

Discussion

Similar to the suggestions provided above, it is possible to derive most insights for each type of restaurant. As restaurant owners, knowing what to do more and what mistakes to avoid is hugely valuable information. Recommendations can be built in a similar fashion that can also help public input the characteristics they are looking for while searching to dine, and recommendations on the most matched places can be provided. This research can be further extended to identify the dishes that a restaurant is most famous for and the ones that are need improvement.

CONCLUSION

Data analytics is radically changing the way the business is strategized. The power of data is still little explored. Deeper analysis of both private and public data can enable innovations that improve customer intimacy, leading to greater customer satisfaction and loyalty. The ability to differentiate a business and drive its market value over its competitors lies largely on leveraging advanced analytics and acting on this intelligence that can eventually produce disruptive new products and services. This research serves as a guide as to how publicly available data could be used to make real-time decisions that could have a material impact on business decisions.

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